

ISic0865

I.Sicily inscription 0865

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἰσπῆς ἔζη
2. σεν ἔτη ιβ
3. μῆνας δ
4. ἡμέρας
5. δ

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Ispes lived for 12 years, 4 months and 4 days

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492493

EDCS 39102019

PHI 140343

PHI 316305

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0048 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 240

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5402b

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